

The relationship between Neotectonics and the Rejuvenation of Euphrates River - IRAQ

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Abstract

The main aim of this study is to determine and find out why it originate the geological-geomorphological phenomenon, known as the "Nagara" which took place in parts of the Euphrates River and its branches (Al-Atshan and Al-Sebil Rivers) at the early twentieth century and continued until the 1940s. It has been confirmed through this study, that the phenomenon of the Nagara, is a geomorphological phenomenon, and it is infact the process of rejuvenating of a part from the Euphrates River and its branches. It's also represented a result of recent tectonic movements in the Southern Iraqi Desert region. The phenomenon of the Nagara was caused by the recent tectonic uplifting of the eastern edge of the Arabian plate, causing the rejuvenation of a part from the Euphrates River and its branches. This tectonic uplifting also, later (at the end 1980s and beginning 1990s) led to river capturing between the Euphrates Branches (Al-Sebil and Al-Atshan). All geological - geomorphological evidences confirm that the recent tectonic activation continues from the Middle and Upper Miocene until today. This is evidenced by this rare geological phenomenon "Al-Nagara", which was not known to the people of Iraq previously, although this area is known as Mesopotamia.

Key words: Morphotectonics, Neotectonic, Rejuvenation of Euphrates River, Nagara, Southern Iraqi Desert, Capture River.

INTRODUCTION

This study concerned with identifying the most important relationship of recent Morphotectonics processes and the Rejuvenation of Euphrates River stream (**photo. 1**), which then caused the river capturing in same section of the river.

Photo (1) shows the rejuvenation of Euphrates River branches (South Al-Shamiya), after (Sousa A., 1946).

The results of this very recent of tectonic activity are represented by activation of subsurface geological structures, especially in the activation of Euphrates fault and others fault in the territory, which formed many geomorphological phenomena. Then we explain the main real scientific reason that was responsible for the occurrence of this phenomenon.

Geologist V.A. Obruchev introduced the term “Neotectonics” in his 1948 article, defining the field as “recent tectonic movements that occurred in the upper part of Tertiary (Neogene) and in the Quaternary, which played an essential role in the origin of the contemporary topography” (Obruchev, 1948). Also the term of “Neotectonics” is defined as the movements of the earth’s crust that occur during the Late Tertiary and Quaternary periods (Vita- Finzi, 1986).

So we find that the definition of Morphotectonics is: a rapidly developing direction of geomorphology, designed to discover the role of tectonic processes in the formation of the Earth surface. The relevance of Morphotectonic studies is due to the need to take into account data on tectonics in the restoration of the history of geological-geomorphological development of any region (Bulochnikova, 2013).

Should be mentioned that sometimes occur certain changes during the cycle of erosion which cause streams to incise their channels with greater vigor. This renewed down cutting is known as rejuvenation. Three principles causes for rejuvenation are: (I) Worldwide changes in sea level, (II) Tectonic changes and (III) Climatic changes (Garde, 2006).

STUDY AREA

The study area is located at latitudes (30° 59' - 31° 56' N) and longitude (46° 12' - 45° 28' E), the area starts from the south of Samawa in the south to Al-Shamiya in the north Fig. (1).

Figure (1): (a) location of the study area from Iraq, (b) Landsat image for the area.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

Structural Geology

The study area is located in two tectonic areas (stable and unstable Shelf) Fig. (2). The first one is the Southern Desert, which represented a part of the northern Arabian Platform, where relatively thin Phanerozoic sediments cover the Precambrian NW – SE and NE –SW fractured continental basement complex while, the Unstable Shelf is located to the east and represented by the Mesopotamia part. The boundary between the two parts of the platform is taken along Euphrates Fault Zone (Ma'ala K., 2009).

Should we mention that the Neotectonic map of Iraq was constructed according to the work of Iraqi- Soviet team during eighties of the last century (Deikran and Sissakian, 2008). The processes which caused a tectonic uplift still continuously work in territory with the formation of a lot of different geological-geomorphological features beneath and on the surface. These processes have taken place at different times, some of them happened in slowly during a long period of time, while others are very fast with clear geological effects (Morphotectonics) on the surface.

Generally, these changes are difficult to be noticed and recorded on maps due to it happened very slowly, but rivers can show that such as changes are particularly

Figure (2): Tectonic map of territory and the rejuvenated part of Euphrates River (Sissakian and Deikran, 1998, Al-Kadhimi *et al.* 1996 and Al-Gurairy, 2000).

noticeable and deduced from the study of topographic maps, and networks of rivers. In addition to the rare phenomena that occur during the human presence in the region, most notably the phenomenon of rejuvenation of river stream. These processes may result in activation of the main of tectonic features, such as growth of domes and anticline folds or formation/activation of faults and others underground features. These processes leave simple superficial effects and may also include movement of the blocks and cause changes on the surface (Al-Qayim, 2011). The stream of the Euphrates River recorded one of the most obvious evidence of the most important Neotectonics activation in the region. Namely (Al-Nagara), is a good example for the rejuvenation of the Euphrates River, which is one of the rare geological-geomorphological processes at the recent time.

Stratigraphy

The main rock units of the area are arranged from base to top, the geological map of the studied area (Fig. 3) shows the following succession:

Figure (3): Geological map of the study area after (Sissakian, 2000 & Jassim and Al-Jiburi, 2009).

1. Dammam Formation (Eocene): is described by Al-Mubarak and Amin (1983) as nummulitic, chalky and dolomitic limestone, 5 – 18 m thick unconformable overlay the upper strata.
2. Ghar Formation (Lower-Miocene): exposed south of Najaf, south of Samawa, north, south and southwest of Busaiya (Al-Sharbati and Ma'ala, 1983a, b and Al-Ani and Ma'ala, 1983a). It consists of basal breccia and red claystone, calcareous sandstone (Al-Mubarak and Amin., 1983; Jassim and Al-Jiburi, 2009) with thickness about (10-26m) (Al-Mubarak and Amin, 1983).
3. Nfayil Formation (Middle Miocene): it is recently renamed by Sissakian *et al.* (1997) as Nfayil Formation. It consists of 15.2-21m of fossiliferous marly limestone and green claystone and yellowish brown calcareous sandstone (Jassim and Al-Jiburi, 2009; Al-Sharbati and Ma'ala 1983 a and b).
4. Quaternary Sediments deposits have a thickness of 6-32m, composed gypcrete and alluvial fan sediments (Pleistocene), valley fill sediments, depression fill sediments and wind-blown sands (Holocene), also mentioned that the Terraces was made at this period (Jassim and Al-Jiburi, 2009).

Geomorphology and Topography

This area are represented by two geomorphological units, they are:

- (I) Structural – Denudational forms like as plateau and tectonic depressions like as Sawa Lake and Samawa Saline Lake, which are developed by strike slip movement along Euphrates Fault Zone (Abu Jir Fault Zone) (Ma'ala K, 2009).

(II) Solutional origin, as Sinkholes and River Karst for example Shat Al-Khasaf.

(III) Aeolian units, such as sand dunes and Nabkha (Al-Gurairy, 2000).

Whereas the average height of surface (6-28 m), where it is decrease from the west to east.

RECENT NEOTECTONICS AND REJUVENATION OF A PART OF EUPHRATES RIVER AND ITS BRANCHES:

The important one example of rejuvenation is the Nile River, which was rejuvenated when the Mediterranean Sea dried up in the late Miocene.

In Iraq, this geological-geomorphological phenomenon has been happened at the end of the 1910s until the mid-1940s. It was started in the stream of the Euphrates River from the south Samawa, towards of upper stream Euphrates River and its branches (Al-Atshan and Al-Sebil) crossing many cities and marshes located at the Euphrates River (Fig. 2). This geomorphological phenomenon was locally designated as (Al-Nagara), which means a waterfall in the stream of the Euphrates River and its branches, in average of high level reach more than 4 m in the major stream, and less than in his branches, as shown in the (Fig. 4).

Figure (4): diagram show the Euphrates River before and after the recent Neotectonics activation .

A. level of the river stream before tectonic activation, B. after

This waterfall was flowing slowly towards the north, which works to reduce the stream of the river bed to about 4 meters, and sometimes more than in the main stream of Euphrates River, which represents the natural eastern border between Mesopotamia and southern Iraqi desert (Fig. 2). This geomorphological phenomenon has continued

until the forties of the twentieth century, when it stopped after all the efforts of the people and government of Iraqi Kingdom to stop it, and prevent it from progress northward in the stream of the Euphrates river and its different branches was failed, which announced by the government in 1938 (Al-Ghurairy, 2000).

This process of rejuvenation of the river stream “Al-Nagara”, was caused by recent geological tectonic movements in the area. Also caused activation process for Euphrates fault, which resulting of the uplifting the area, which making the stream deepens its level in order to restore the natural balance to its stream. Which that prevailed before as Morphotectonic activation, as shown in (Figure 2).The main cause for the occurring this process is the rejuvenation of the Euphrates fault, which caused the uplifting of the earth at the eastern parts of the Southern Desert. This uplifting caused in the uplifting of Euphrates water level which caused in the appearance of Al-Nagaradue to the rebalancing the river level with its natural level.

Main causes for the rejuvenation of Euphrates River

The recent Neotectonic movements influencing in the activation of many faults and folds below the surface, caused the increasing of Morphotectonic activities in this region, and its neighboring areas, causing prominent changes in the main stream of the Euphrates River from west to east (Fig. 2, 5).

Figure (5): the boundary of stable shelf in territory after (Fouad Safa F.A., 2007).

The stable shelf represents the extension of the Arabian Shield, which also represents its eastern edges, due to the convergent movement of the Arabic, Iranian and Turkish plates.

These processes have resulted in the continued activation of the Euphrates fault, as well as the uplifting of the eastern edges of the stable shelf, which proved by many recent studies (Al-Nagash A. B. and Al-Jubory M. S., 1989, and AL-Khersan Emad H. 1999). They also caused the continuous tectonic activation of the ancient faults associated with the basement rocks, also the formation of new faults that are different in depths and extension (Al-Abdan R. H. and Al-Gurairy A. S. Y., 2017), (Fig. 6).

Figure (6): Continental Drift of the Arabian Plate from Eocene to present, after (GLENNIE, 1992)

The long profile shows how, in the upper stage of a river's course, where the river's gradient is steep but it gradually flattens out as the river erodes towards its base level, (Fig. 7). Should be noted, the presence of knickpoints "waterfall" in the longitudinal profile of River stream.

Figure (7): the longitudinal profile of River stream and the Rejuvenation.

These are points where the gradient of the river changes suddenly and can be caused by landforms or also by rejuvenation due to Tectonic activation "Tectonic uplift", where the base level of the river falls giving it some extra gravitational potential energy to erode vertically. In the Euphrates River and its branches appeared landfalls about (2 – more 4 m) from south of Samawa to north of Gammas city, through a distance about more than 140 Km. This waterfall "Al-Nagara" continued more than 27 years, which where was going slowly about less than (5.2 Km / year) from south to north (Sousa A., 1946 and Al-Gurairy, 2000), in flat areas where people were not familiar with the existence of waterfalls in the riverbeds there. This geological - geomorphological phenomenon caused panic of for Iraqi people living in this time, which they did not know before, especially in Mesopotamia.

The river capture

The recent Neotectonic movements influencing the activation of many folds and faults beneath the surface, which caused the increasing of Morphotectonic activities on the surface, such as changing main stream of the Euphrates River from west to east (Fig. 8), are named in geomorphology as "River capture".

Figure (8): Recent Morphotectonics and River Capture (Euphrates branches)

A- Euphrates River.

B- The Part of Al-Atshan river, which was affected by recent Tectonic activation.

C- The old main stream (Al-Atshan River), before the capture river.

D- Al-Sebil River became the main stream after the 1990s.

The Al-Atshan River was the main stream of the Euphrates River, while the river of the Al-Sebil was one of the main branches of the Euphrates River. However, the situation changed in the late 1980s and early 1990s, after changing the discharge of all the Euphrates River water to the Al-Sebil river, whereas Al-Atshan become a dry river. This phenomenon indicates the continuation of recent tectonic activity according to two main possibilities:

A- Continuation of tectonic uplifting, or

B- Activation of sub-surface geological formations in this area.

CONCLUSIONS

This study proved that the Euphrates river region is still tectonically very active, and this activation has continued from the late Miocene to the present day. Also, this study highlighted a rare geological-geomorphological phenomenon that occurred in the stream of the Euphrates River, which is the rejuvenation a part of the Euphrates River and its branches, as a result of the recent tectonic activation of the faults system in the region. Also, the process of river capture that took place between the river Al-Sebil and the river Al-Atshan is due to this modern and continuous recent tectonic activation.

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